

Subject: Research: Technical Debt Prioritization

Hi **developer.name OR developer.login**,

My name is ******** and I am a Ph.D. Candidate in Computer Science (*******). Under the guidance of my advisor we are conducting a study to develop context-adaptive methods using machine learning approach to prioritize the technical debt items payment in real software projects.

You can contribute to the research project by answering some questions about technical debt in the **{{project.name}}** project. [Click here](#) or visit <https://URL?project=pr1&user=1> to participate.

Learn more about the research project by visiting our website <http://URL>

If you have any questions or want to make any comments, please contact us by email *******.

Why participate in the research? By participating in this research you will be contributing to the development of an intelligent method of technical debt prioritization. At the end of the project, we will make available a technical debt prioritization tool and videos teaching how to manage technical debt using the tool.

What is technical debt? In software-intensive systems, technical debt is a design or implementation construct that is expedient in the short term, but sets up a technical context that can make a future change more costly or impossible. Technical debt is a contingent liability whose impact is limited to internal system qualities, primarily maintainability and evolvability. - [Dagstuhl Seminar on Technical Debt Research](#)

Consent Terms You can see the informed consent for participation in research activities [clicking here](#) or accessing [URL](#).

Thanks,

Researcher and Ph.D Candidate

If you no longer wish to receive such messages, [click here](#).

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